

Teacher and Student Relationship- A study

Paper Id : 18610 Submission Date : 01/02/2024 Acceptance Date : 16/02/2024 Publication Date : 20/02/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10907741

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Samaresh Nath

Associate Professor
Education
Fakiragram College
Assam,India

Abstract

Teacher education occupied a central place in the total programmed of education. It is the key to qualitative improvement of education in the students and leaning environment in a country. The teacher is the backbone of the society who guides the students to proceed to the path of the light of knowledge and skills to the improvement of humanities. The county largely depends on the classroom and the fate of the students in the classrooms is being shaped by the teacher and the better relationship with student of society. Students call for new teaching skills technique have entered the classroom and communication there students for good environment. The student's individual and their families socially hope demand value for their education and desire more efficiency, effective through teaching and Learning activities among student. The relationship between teachers & students are getting we can expect such effective teaching from teachers who are fully aware of different methods. Our teachers are always improved vital role in the new educational pedagogy used in developed society and countries.

Keywords Teacher, Student, Society and Relationship.

Introduction

Teachers need to understand modern pedagogies first and develop their own understanding before inventing the skills that will work best for our students. Our students are very energetic so they able to keep silence and concentration to the teacher. A successful teacher is mandatorily not the one, who knows well, but the one who creates a positive, creative and life changing impact on his / her students. Now comes the part where we can say that a teacher is not complete without the students and vice versa. Teacher deep insight, appropriate knowledge, right attitude and required skills for teaching. It enable teacher to grasp the underlying principles and critical methods of teaching, developed a mental culture to appreciate fundamental concept and develop their own free judgment and sense of intellectual in educational field for the Students relationship with society. As the trends of technology and society changes, so do the teacher student relationships. In early ages, we have seen the students and disciples touch the feet of teachers as a mark of respect. In today's world respect to teacher and students environment more understanding in every places specially our guru mean teachers in the society.

Aim of study

We will explore the nature of relationship between teachers and their students in education environment in India.

The specific objectives are given below...

1. To find out traditionally from Vedic, Buddhist and medieval period teacher student-relations.
2. To know the perception of teachers about their students in all level educational in situations.
3. To explore the inherent talent students by developing teacher-student relationships.
4. To examine the impact of teacher-student relationship on student's learning.

**Review of
Literature**

Mc Affrey, et.al, (2003), revealed that, teachers' classrooms behavior or management of educational activities in the institution play important role to give quality education to university students. To investigate the teachers' quality, students were asked about lesson clarity, instructional variety and "teacher's effective time management".

Among the respondents, 80 percent replied positively when asked them whether the teachers make the lesson clear and 15 percent replied negatively and 5 percent made no comment on it. Most of the students added that junior teacher's quality is not up to the mark and senior teachers are very busy and not updated about tools, techniques and evidence. According to 70 percent respondents, most of the teachers both from senior and junior level are very stereotype to deliver their lecture in the class room, 20 percent respondents viewed that few teachers follow interactive techniques in class room and rest of the respondents made no comment on it. Among the selected respondents 56 percent have expressed their positive responses about the class conducted by their teachers regularly and 44 percent given the negative responses in this regard.

Monem, (2007), described that, the present method of teaching in basic subjects are ineffective because of outmoded method and lack of philosophical under. In addition,

students' dissatisfaction and their comment about quality of teachers indirectly showed that there are gaps in lecture delivery and making the class interactive using different instructional style. In teacher's recruitment political loyalty or family relationship or any other group identity get priority over the merit.

Rahman & Islam, (2011), stated that, in public universities, an irregularity in class taking is a common phenomenon. In many cases chairmen of departments and directors of institutes failed to convince the senior to conduct class regularly. Without taking regular class, senior teachers complete the class by a few lectures or he handovers the class relatively to junior teacher of the same department or same institute.

Khan, (2010), stated that, university authority irrespective of political regime over the decades preferred recruiting 'voters', not 'teachers' that adversely affected the quality of university education. many Associate Professors and Professors of public universities who do not have any research based degree (M. Phil and Ph.D. degrees) are supervising M. Phil and PhD students.

Islam, (2010), stated that, under promotion restructuring rules, academically weak candidates without having a MS and PhD with minimum number of publications in local journals (non-referred journals) receive promotion to next higher position on the basis of length of service in the public universities.

Konti, (2011) examined that, students are not concern about effective application but teachers are much concerned about their application.

Ayalew, (2016), shown that, there was no statically significant difference between teacher and their students' assessment practice.

Antoniou, Kyriakides and Creemers, (2009), stated that, educational effectiveness depends on teachings kills Their study also suggested that better students' output depends on teaching differentiation, advanced skills, advanced behaviors and new teachings approach etc.

Leoanak and Amalo, (2018), found that, during an interaction of classroom, the students are highly motivated by the performance of the teacher.

Hattie, (2015), identify a number of influences related to effective learning, some of these influences included teaching strategies, classroom discussion, classroom cohesion, teacher expectation, teacher immediacy, teacher credibility and classroom behaviour. Establishing a positive and supportive classroom environment, combined with productive relationships between teachers and their students, will provide a platform in which students are encouraged and motivated to grow both academically and personally.

Bridget & Rober, (2001),

Recognized that, the inherent qualities of a student-teacher relationship and a teacher's rapport with students resulted in a classroom environment where students were affirmed

and supported to achieve their best. Student – Teacher connection in clinical nursing education.

Gillespie, (2002), stated that, students who have positive relationships with their teachers are more willing to take on academic challenges and work on their social-emotional development **Das (1930)** declared that in the Vedic tradition the students would be encouraged to approach the teacher with enquiries. The teaching system was individualized and the teacher would instruct each student separately. This way has created numerous opportunities to evaluate the students' capacities and adapt this

approach whenever needed (Das, 1930: 134).

Through close relationships, the teacher should understand the needs of the student better and teach him according to his individual needs. This naturally motivates the student to closely follow the teacher's instructions with a sense of belonging. According to Alnassery (2019), when students are feeling respected by their teachers, they focus more on learning, become more motivated, and thus the learning process for them becomes very smooth. The students described that as 'feeling at ease'. On the other hand, Ibrahim (2019) points out that negative relationships lead to student's low sense of school belonging.

Das (1930) further stated that a function of education is to determine the greatest potential of each individual and to direct him in his education. He argues that the pedagogical principle and the formulation of the ancient Indian is ideal for a liberal education (**Das, 1930: 7**).

Yan (2019) too confirms the effective teacher-student relationship may promote students' learning and that understanding the dynamics of this relationship is very Nat. Volatiles & Essent. Oils, 2021; 8(6): 5243-5247 5246 important in students' learning and thus more research should be conducted in this field to find more practical ideas and methods for teachers.

Successful training of a student under the Vedic educational system requires strict discipline from both the student and teacher likewise. For the student to endure the demands, close relationship with his teacher is necessary. In this regards, Das (1930) gives us a view of the requirements and ways for such close relationships to successfully develop: "In order to achieve this high ideal of perfect mastery over the senses, a life of strict discipline was prescribed for the student. He had to shun sensual pleasures of all kinds and lead a simple austere life. He was inspired by the high ideals of the teacher with whom he lived in close and intimate contact and imbibed social and moral virtues by his precept and example. At the same time the tender side of his nature was nourished and domestic virtues developed by the sweet and affectionate relationship with the wife and children of the teacher." (Das, 1930: 26)

Methodology

A study student- teacher's relation between society and educational environment. Own my observation theoretical as well as no experimental there are data from internet, books and other sources. This methodology use secondary our views actually development our society and interest of all level of education.

Result and Discussion

Study teacher and student relation is very important role of society and our environment from the Guru and shishyas Gurukul to medieval and modern society-

Vedic age- the relation between the "Guru(teacher) and Shisyas(student) was just like of father and son relation "guru(teacher) very affectionately looked after his "taught" he never let them suffer in any way and always tried for their all-round development.

Buddhist the post-Vedic period- the teacher and taught relationship remained the same as in the Vedic age .the teacher earned almost respect from his student and he treated them like his own sons and always worked and cared for their development. The students were expected to serve their teacher with humanity.

The teacher treated his discipline like his own sons, and arranged for all kind of facilities need by the taught, as like that footing, lodging, clothing treatment during sickness etc. In fact taught lived like the family member of the teacher .some of the students became so closely connected with their teacher they remained with them for their whole life and home past. The guru 9teacher used to examine his "shishyas/student very thoroughly and would never give the knowledge of true absolute to a student who failed in his examination. Mr.N.N Mazumdar says,- "*in ancient times the greatest care was used to discover the attitude and fitness of and*

individual to receive any particular kind of education Mantrayan Brahman, Apanished, clearly adores that the knowledge of absolute should be given only to those student who have been full faith with guru /teacher are process technique and special talent to understand subject.

Teacher student relation 21st century-

In modern age of education policy always productive and skill based teaching learning pedagogy in the all level on educational activities from traditional is back born of our classroom efficiencies .Twenty first century Also guru and taught relationship most powerful attachment for the success in filed both guru and taught as well as classroom management such relationship are the most significant factor in assigned in determining a teacher's work as successful life. It is vital that student respect their teacher as professional activities. at the beginning of their career teacher often face difficulties in establishing a strong and healthy relationship, as they are very closed to the students age and lack experience. Sometimes in experienced teacher estblish too close relationship with student, which can later generate various problems in classroom discipline and education can make both student and other teacher lose their respect. Effective teaching does not require that all student like the teacher, however it is crucial that they all respected teacher and student, teacher also do not need to like their entire student. They just need to be professionals and leaders student do not to be friends with teacher they need to respect from Lerner. Most of the student doesn't know respect their Guru is a Brahma. Student are too young and do not experience who to respect with each other that friendship but specially Guru.

A strong and positive relationship with student is also very important for classroom success. Teacher can learn and use various techniques and approaches to strengthen and improve the quality of the relationship with his or her student, such techniques can help boost the students commitment and participation in skilled base pedagogy.

Conclusion

Teacher student relationship most important with discipline. There are student free and respected of society in key role in teacher and student relationship. However their discipline would merely serve as a means of maintaining a healthy from Vedic, Buddhist, and 21st century to continuing period Indian culture classroom environment of our society there are discipline should not to be a goal for its own sake skills development for teacher in classroom discipline by making to their interest investment mentally, physically, emotionally and educationally for all level of education. Quality of higher education in India is not at the level to match international standard which is considered to be essential to cope with the upcoming challenges that world is confronted with. Many researchers found that quality of higher education is deteriorating day by day. The effects of teacher-student relationships have been researched extensively, positive relationships can have good social and Academic outcomes. Its' important to understand how to develop positive teacher -student relationships, so we can get best outcomes inside and outside the classroom.

References

1. Antoniou, Kyriakides and Creemers, (2009). "Teacher behaviour and student outcomes: Suggestions for research on teacher training and professional development." Teaching and TeacherEducation. Vol.25, No.1, p.12-23.
2. Profe, B,C Rai, History of Indian education Robert Ullich, History of educational thought Florence Stratemeyer Margaret kind secy Ayalew, M. Z, (2016). "Teachers' and Students' Perceptions towards the Practice of Assessment of Learning: Implication for Future Job Performance of Would Be Graduates".
3. American Journal of Educational Research, Vol. 4, No.12.
4. Bridget K. Hamre, Robert C. Pianta, (2001). "Early Teacher-Child Relationships Hattie, John, (2015). "Hattie Ranking: 252 Influences And Effect Sizes Related To Student Achievement." Panon Press Ltd, Canada.
5. Islam, F (2007), "Some issues of higher education in Bangladesh: Analysis of demand, problems and trends," The Financial Express, 27 Jun.
6. Khan, M. M (2010), "State of Public Universities in Bangladesh", The Daily Star, The Independence Day Special Issue, 26 March.

7. Konti, F, (2011). "Teachers and Students Perceptions towards teacher's classroom management applications in primary schools". *Procedia- Social and Behavioral Sciences*, Vol.15, pp. 4093-4097.
8. Leoanak, S.P.P. and Amalo, B.K.(2018). "Teacher's behavior towards students' motivation practice". *Global Conference on Teaching, Assessment, and Learning in Education (GC-TALE 2017)*, 42, Article No. 00078.
9. Mc Caffrey, D.F, Lockwood, J. R., Koretz, D., Louis, T.A. & Hamilton, L. (2004) "Modes of valueadded modeling of teacher effects". *Journal of Educational and Behavioral Statistics*, Vol. 29, No.1, pp.67-101.
10. Monem, M (2007), "Higher Education in Bangladesh: Status, Issues and Prospects". in Gamage Sujata(2007) ed. *Higher Education in Bangladesh, Malaysia, Philippines and Sri Lanka* ; Sri lanka Education Forum. Rahman, M. M, and Islam, S. (2011), "Higher Education Vying for quantity or quality?" *The Daily Star*, January 8.
11. Shigh,L.C & Mishra,s.(2005) *Quality concerns in teacher Education*, University News,43(18),Alnassery, Y. (2014) – *Impact of Students-Teacher Relationship on Student's Learning – A Review of Literature*. *IJONE Journal* January-June2014-II-05-1-201411
- 12.Das, S.K. (1930) – *The Educational System of Ancient Hindus*. Calcutta, India.
13. Ibrahim, A., Zataari, W.E. (2019) – *The teacher–student relationship and adolescents' sense of school belonging*. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*. DOI: 10.1080/02673843.2019.1660998
14. Kaufman, S.R., Sandilos L. (2010) – *Improving Students' Relationships with Teachers to Provide Essential Supports for Learning*. American Psychological Association.
15. Lee, J.S. (2012) – *The effects of the teacher–student relationship and academic press on student engagement and academic performance*. *International Journal of Educational Research* 53 (2012) 330-340. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijer.2012.04.006